

THE ROLE OF EDMUND SPENCER WITH ENGLISH AND UZBEK SPEECH CULTURE IN THE ART OF ENGLISH SPEECH

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Abstract: In this article, we will provide you with information about the English speech culture, as well as conduct a comparative study of it with the UZBEK language. Through our article, you will get acquainted with the work and brief life of Edmund Spencer, who made a significant contribution to the formation of the English speech culture, raised the English speech culture with his oratorical art, and was the author of several elegant poetic works.

Key words: English speech culture, speech etiquette, lexicon, means of communication, semantic unit.

Speech culture, first of all, following the norms of the correct, literary language is to speak. A high level of speech culture is indispensable for a cultured person is feature. It is the duty of each of us to improve our speech. Of this error in pronunciation, use of word forms, sentence construction we must watch our speech in order not to. [1;43-p]

Speech culture, speech etiquette: 1) norms of oral and written literary language (pronunciation, accent, vocabulary, grammar, stylistic rules) acquisition as well as the ability to use the figurative means of the language in accordance with the purpose and content of the speech in various communication –intervention situations; 2) the branch of linguistics that studies the problems of standardization (regulation) in order to perfect the language as a tool of culture. In Western linguistics, the term „language culture” is also used in a general sense. The concept of „speech culture “ in the 1st sense covers two stages of mastering the literary language: a) correctness of speech and other speech skills. The correctness of speech is adherence to literary standards perceived by speakers and writers of a particular language as „ideal “ or universally accepted and traditionally preserved customs, examples and examples. Speech skill is not only to follow literary standards, but also to choose the most correct, clearest, most appropriate and expressive in terms of style and situation from among the available options. Speech culture is a social phenomenon, which develops in close

“CONFERENCE OF NATURAL AND APPLIED SCIENCES IN SCIENTIFIC INNOVATIVE RESEARCH”

Issue 1. January 2024

connection with the development of society , science and technology, culture and literary life. As the cultural level of the members of the society increases , their speech becomes polished and polished , improving in accordance with the rules and norms of speech culture . Literature, art , radio, television and periodical press have a special place in the formation and development of speech culture . Lexicography , in particular , explanatory , spelling , pronunciation , educational and other special dictionaries are important in the standardization of literary language and the development of the theory of speech culture. The broad concept of culture is , of course , the culture of communication , the culture of speech behavior.[2;12-p]

Speech etiquette refers to the linguistic signs and rules of their use currently accepted in this society in order to establish a speech connection between interlocutors and ensure communication in an emotionally positive tonality in accordance with the speech situation. For example, Uzbek and English speech etiquette phrases : hello/hi , how are you ?how are you?, with my respect , let me introduce it is an honor to introduce ;welcome ,welcome/here you are ,nice appetite/bon appetite, with best wishes bread and salt, tea and sugar, God supposes; thank you, save Christ Help, please, let me express my deepest gratitude; be healthy / stat healthy, see you again, khayr/goodbye, etc.[4;2-p]

Speech etiquette is a universal language phenomenon that, Uzbek and English language have . At the same time , each language has its own vocabulary of words and phrases that reflect the national specificity of politeness of speech . English and uzbek language Greetings. Nice to meet you Nice to meet you Make an offer. Would you like ..? Do you want..? Apologize Excuse me, I am sorry

Can you do me a favor?

May I/Can you help me ?

The rules of speech etiquette are regulated by the rules of speech etiquette –a system of stable expressions developed in spoken language and used in situation of establishing and maintaining communication . This appeal : Dear Sir or Madam salomlar Good morning et cetera like to invite you tips : I would like to recommend you and other things . Speech etiquette includes everything that conveys a friendly attitude to the interlocutor , creates a comfortable environment for communication.

A rich collection of language tools allows you to choose what is suitable for the speech situation and convenient for the addressee, you or you form of

“CONFERENCE OF NATURAL AND APPLIED SCIENCES IN SCIENTIFIC INNOVATIVE RESEARCH”

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communication, setting a friendly, simple or, on the contrary, formal tone of conversation.

In general, by comparing some lexical semantic groups specific to speech etiquettes in Uzbek and English, their comparative study will be of great importance to reflect the rules of etiquette and culture in these language.

Thus, the above was the same developed speech culture. Edmund Spenser made a great contribution to the development of English speech culture. He is a prolific creator of English poetic poetry. Edmund Spenser, who went down in history as a poet who embodied the art of speech along with the culture of speech, was born in London in 1551/1552.

Wealth with livestock. Spenser, a relative of a noble family, born in a simple family, became a nobleman in the future with his oratorical art and creative work. In time, he studied art at the University of Cambridge. He reached the peak of this direction by studying the poetic art of the writers who created before him.

In the poetry of Edmund Spenser, the reader was distinguished by a special elegance, skillful of words. In turn, our hero created an opportunity for his poetic works to reach the heart of the reader with the art of oratory. An importance aspect of his work was that he was able to penetrate all layers of society with his poems.

It is no exaggeration to say that his poems have taken the English speech culture to another level. Being called the „Prince of Poets “ is a clear example of how high a place he holds in the art of English poetry, as well as in speech culture.

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